

HEX: Agentic Retrieval Framework for Healthcare Entity Table Generation

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Abstract. Most of the Retrieval-augmented Generation (RAG) frameworks treat list-based queries as an entity generation, failing when answers require multi-attribute information of entities. We define this problem as a high-recall retrieval task of synthesizing structured entity table from web sources. While agentic retrieval frameworks can autonomously browse the web to retrieve information, they lack effective query reformulation and structured boundaries necessary to aggregate web entities into a comprehensive table. To address these limitations, we introduce HEX, a six-state agentic framework that leverages LLM-based decision making within state-machine boundaries. HEX ensures exhaustive retrieval of entities and their attributes to generate a comprehensive table. Evaluating HEX against state-of-the-art baselines across three healthcare tasks demonstrate that HEX improves entity recall while maintaining high precision.

Keywords: AI agent · Entity Retrieval · Agentic Information Retrieval.

1 Introduction

Most queries are best answered with comprehensive lists (e.g., hospitals in Ontario or police misconduct cases in Tennessee between 2020 and 2024). The key features of these queries are their spatial (e.g., Toronto, California) and temporal (2020-2024) components. Their spatial components further divided into two distinct regions: micro (e.g., Toronto) and macro (e.g., Tennessee). The scale of these regions directly governs the retrieval complexity and determines the comprehensiveness of the final list. Examples of such queries are provided in Figure 1.

Existing RAG frameworks treat list queries as a passive extraction task [8]. These frameworks also struggle with duplicate entities within the final list [15]. They assume that entities are unique strings and remove duplicate entities. However, in some cases duplicate entities cannot simply be removed if they appear multiple times. For instance, the Canadian Mental Health Association (CMHA)

Fig. 1. Example 1 and 2 represent list-based queries with their underlying intent

cannot be treated as a redundant entity because CMHA Guelph is distinct from CMHA Toronto. This geographical distinction shifts the problem from List Generation to Table Generation, where extracted entities must be accompanied by specific attributes such as location, description, and contact information. While question answering over tables [7] has been extensively explored, a significant gap remains in the inverse task of generating structured tables from distributed web sources. In this study, we define these table generation tasks as a high-recall retrieval problem, termed as *Comprehensive Retrieval*.

Recent studies have extensively explored RAG and agentic retrieval frameworks for factoid, long-context, and multi-hop question answering tasks [6], [16]. In the absence of recall-oriented frameworks, we adapt and evaluate these RAG and agentic frameworks for the comprehensive retrieval problem. Our findings reveal that these frameworks lack effective query reformulation and schema awareness for mapping entities to attributes necessary to aggregate web entities into a comprehensive table for agentic retrieval.

To address these limitations, we propose HEX (named after its six-states) designed for agentic retrieval, which is specifically optimized for structured table generation. HEX governs the retrieval process through six states leveraging agentic reasoning within the state-machine boundaries. HEX allows the agent to explore deep web sources systematically, and transforms unstructured web documents into schema-aligned information tables.

In this study, we evaluated HEX for macro-region comprehensive retrieval task queries requiring exhaustive entity discovery. We compared HEX to RAG and agentic frameworks across three healthcare tasks (hospitals, addiction treatment & community mental healthcare). Our results demonstrate that HEX achieves superior retrieval coverage and output accuracy compared to existing SOTA. To ensure the reproducibility of our findings and to support future research in comprehensive retrieval tasks, we release our scripts, experimental artifacts, and dataset ⁴.

In summary, the main contributions of this paper are:

1. We identify and formally define the comprehensive retrieval task, shifting the objective from list generation toward comprehensive table generation.
2. We design and implement HEX, a framework that integrates a state machine architecture with agentic reasoning.
3. We conduct evaluations against RAG and agentic baselines on three healthcare tasks, demonstrating that HEX achieves superior retrieval coverage and accuracy.

2 Related Work

The evolution of intelligent information systems has transitioned from static retrieval-augmented architectures to active, goal-oriented agentic paradigms. Early advancements focused heavily on enhancing Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) pipelines [16], [9]. Subsequent studies introduced specialized optimizations such as iterative query reformulation [5], re-ranking [11], and fine-grained evidence density refinement [4] to maximize precision and overcome basic retrieval constraints. While these RAG enhancements significantly improve factual grounding and address structural data noise [2], they are inherently designed to provide precise answers. When tasked with comprehensive retrieval, RAG systems fail because they lack the active exploration policies necessary to systematically discover and aggregate hundreds of entities and attributes across the web to construct tables.

To bridge this gap, recent literature has shifted toward agentic information retrieval (Agentic IR), which conceptualizes web search as an interactive, task-solving process [18]. Frameworks like ReAct [20] and WebShop [19] demonstrated the viability of utilizing LLMs as reasoning engines that can navigate web interfaces and manage tool calls. More recent advancements have successfully extended agentic search loops to multi-hop question answering [21], source bias mitigation [13], query reformulation [12], and automated data collection pipelines [1], [3]. However, existing agentic frameworks are fundamentally constrained to short-horizon retrieval chains or single-target extraction tasks [14]. Our work directly addresses these limitations by introducing a multi-state agentic framework optimized to perform long-horizon web search, systematically navigating extensive web sources to construct schema-aligned tables.

⁴ <https://github.com/LabBioAI/HEX>

Fig. 2. Overview of HEX. Planning states decompose and reformulate input query into localized search queries, while retrieval states retrieve, extract, and verify entity-centric information from the web to construct a comprehensive table.

3 Problem Formulation

We formalize comprehensive information retrieval as a high-recall table generation problem, where the objective is to systematically retrieve, extract, and aggregate entities and their attributes distributed across the Web into a structured table. Given a search task $T = (q_t, \mathcal{A})$, the task query $q_t = (I_s, I_c)$ comprises two components: I_s denotes the semantic intent (e.g., *hospitals*), and I_c denotes the scope constraints encapsulating spatial boundaries (e.g., *Ontario*) or temporal windows. The target attribute schema $\mathcal{A} = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_D\}$ represents a finite set of D distinct attributes specified by task requirements (e.g., *address*, *contact details*, *service description*). The ultimate objective is to construct a comprehensive knowledge table $\mathcal{K} = \{(e_i, \mathbf{a}_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ where e_i denotes a unique extracted entity satisfying the constraints of both I_s and I_c , and $\mathbf{a}_i = [a_{i,1}, a_{i,2}, \dots, a_{i,D}]$ represents a D -dimensional attribute vector where each element $a_{i,j}$ corresponds to the extracted textual or numeric value for the specific attribute label $A_j \in \mathcal{A}$.

4 Method

We propose HEX, a framework that leverages agentic reasoning within a state machine architecture \mathcal{M} to generate comprehensive tables. As illustrated in Figure 2, HEX partitions the end-to-end table generation into a state space \mathcal{S} split across search planning and retrieval states. Within an active state, language

model β evaluates state-specific context, invokes tools τ , and executes state transitions δ . By confining agentic reasoning within state machine boundaries, the framework restricts the tool-use and context space of β to the active sub-task, which is designed to maximize information recall.

4.1 HEX: Agentic Retrieval Framework

HEX is designed as a directed state machine \mathcal{M} to process comprehensive IR tasks and construct a structured entity-attribute table. Formally, we define the state machine as a tuple $\mathcal{M} = \langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{U}, \delta \rangle$, where:

- \mathcal{S} (State Space): A finite set of states $\mathcal{S} = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_6\}$, structurally divided into Planning States (S_1, S_2, S_3) and Retrieval States (S_4, S_5, S_6). HEX execution is initialized at a designated starting state $S_{init} = S_1$ upon receiving the task query Q_t , and terminates at a final state $S_{term} = S_6$ when table \mathcal{K} is generated.
- \mathcal{U} (Action Space): The set of actions available to the agent. The language model β evaluates the state context, invokes a specialized tool τ , and determines the actionable decision $a \in \mathcal{U}$.
- δ (Transition Function): The transition function defined as $\delta : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$ that governs the progression of the agent through the state space. Based on the action a decided by the language model β within the active state S_i , HEX computes the next state:

$$S' = \delta(S_i, a) \quad (1)$$

where $S' \in \mathcal{S}$ represents the subsequent state, enabling dynamic branching (e.g., state bypassing), iterative self-looping (e.g., executing batched queries sequentially or extracting data entity-by-entity), or task termination.

Query Analysis (S_1): In this state, HEX analyzes and classifies the query’s comprehensive scope I_c . HEX selects a routing action $a \in \{\text{comprehensive, lookup}\}$, where task complexity is governed directly by the scale of the target region. A *comprehensive* action is chosen if the query comprises a macro-region requiring multi-layered search (e.g., "*hospitals in Ontario*"). Conversely, a *lookup* action is selected if query contains a micro-region (e.g., "*hospitals in Toronto*"). HEX treats temporal constraints like lookup tasks and routes directly to S_4 . Temporal constraints are not decomposed because search engines do not index webpages based on temporal granularity. Hex then executes a state transition based on this action:

$$\delta(S_1, a) = \begin{cases} S_4, & \text{if } a = \text{lookup} \\ S_2, & \text{if } a = \text{comprehensive} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

When $a = \text{lookup}$, HEX transitions directly to the agentic retrieval state (S_4), bypassing the intermediate planning states to minimize execution latency. When $a = \text{comprehensive}$, HEX transitions to S_2 for query decomposition.

Query Decomposition (S_2): In this state, HEX invokes a Knowledge Graph τ_{KG} to decompose the macro-region into a finite set of M geographic sub-regions:

$$\mathcal{Z}_{sub} = \{z_1, z_2, \dots, z_M\} \quad (3)$$

This process is termed *Knowledge-augmented Query Decomposition*. After this, HEX transitions to S_3 for query reformulation of each sub-region.

Query Reformulation (S_3): In this state, HEX reformulates the sub-regions \mathcal{Z}_{sub} into a set of search queries \mathcal{Q} :

$$\mathcal{Q} = \{\beta(z_i) \mid z_i \in \mathcal{Z}_{sub}\} \quad (4)$$

HEX utilizes in-context learning to ensure that each $q_i \in \mathcal{Q}$ remains contextually aligned with the primary task query q_t while being uniquely optimized for its respective sub-region z_i .

Agentic Retrieval (S_4): To scale agentic information retrieval to complex web environments, Agentic Retrieval operates as a stateful tracking rather than a linear tool. Web environments require interaction with JavaScript-heavy web-pages, so agentic retrieval uses a search and browse paradigm as follows:

$$\mathcal{D}_i = \{\tau_c(\tau_p(\tau_b(u))) \mid u \in \tau_s(q_i) \setminus \mu\} \quad (5)$$

HEX executes the retrieval process only once for lookup tasks. Following the analysis of S_1 , temporal and micro-region queries are routed as a lookup task, so HEX runs retrieval for them once. For information retrieval, HEX invokes the search engine τ_s to retrieve a set of the top- k URLs for the reformulated query $q_i \in \mathcal{Q}$. Then, it utilizes a headless browsing tool τ_b to visit each unique URL u . This runtime browsing ensures that client-side JavaScript settles before the parser tool τ_p extracts the HTML from the URL. To prevent infinite execution loops, the agentic retrieval is strictly limited to loading the primary target webpage without navigating further to secondary hyperlinks. Finally, a markdown converter tool τ_c transforms the HTML into Markdown document $d \in \mathcal{D}_i$. This workflow preserves the layout structure of the webpage while eliminating HTML token noise for downstream extraction.

This state also maintains a session memory μ containing all previously visited URLs. After retrieving URLs, HEX cross-references the newly retrieved URLs against μ . If a URL is already present in μ , the agent skips it and moves to the next candidate. Conversely, if a URL is fresh, the browsing tool τ_b is invoked, and the URL is appended to μ . This memory is maintained for the duration of the complete search session, spanning from the input task query q_t to the generation of the final table \mathcal{K} . To process the complete query batch \mathcal{Q} sequentially, the framework executes an iterative self-loop over this state. At the completion of each iteration i , the local document subset is accumulated into the global document search space, defined at termination as $\mathcal{D} = \bigcup_{q_i \in \mathcal{Q}} \mathcal{D}_i$.

Information Extraction (S_5): In this state, HEX extracts entity-attribute pairs from web documents $d \in \mathcal{D}$. To ensure structured and precise extraction, HEX leverages schema A , formalized as:

$$\mathcal{E} = \{\beta(A, d) \mid d \in \mathcal{D}\} \quad (6)$$

where each element $e \in \mathcal{E}$ represents a structured entity instance whose key-value attributes strictly conform to the fields specified in A .

Information Verification (S_6): Grounded in information quality (IQ) theory [17], the final state of HEX evaluates the extracted entity set \mathcal{E} to enforce rigorous information quality control before generating the final table \mathcal{K} . Rather than relying on simple heuristic filtering, HEX leverages the LLM β to systematically assess each extracted entity instance $e \in \mathcal{E}$ across two core IQ dimensions against the task description D_t and task query q_t : *intrinsic semantic accuracy* (verifying core topical alignment) and *contextual accuracy* (verifying specific spatial or temporal constraints). Capitalizing on the in-context learning capabilities of LLMs, β acts as a quality assessor to assign a binary relevance label $r \in \{0, 1\}$ alongside a graded confidence score $s \in [0, 1]$ to ($r = 1$). Entity instances failing this dual-verification ($r = 0$) are truncated from the table \mathcal{K} . The verification pipeline is formalized as:

$$\mathcal{K} = \{(e, s) \mid e \in \mathcal{E} \wedge \beta_r(e, D_t, q_t) = 1, \text{ where } s = \beta_s(e, D_t, q_t)\} \quad (7)$$

The final output \mathcal{K} is structured as a JSON Lines (JSONL) file, where each discrete line represents a row in the final table, and the entity-attribute fields represent the columns.

5 Experiments

HEX is implemented using LangGraph, providing a graph-based structure to build AI agents. Each node in LangGraph maps to a state $S = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_6\}$, with edges governing the transition logic (δ). In our framework, different LLMs can be utilized by modifying the configuration file. For our experiments, we utilized `gpt-4o-2024-11-20`, with the temperature parameter set to 0. The LLM is accessed via the official OpenAI API.

5.1 Experimental Setting

To evaluate our method, our experiment answer the following research questions (RQs):

- **RQ1 (Main Findings):** How does HEX perform compared to existing state-of-the-art methods?
- **RQ2 (Analysis):** How does HEX maximize entity recall while maintaining precision?
- **RQ3 (Task Generalization):** How robustly does HEX generalize across healthcare tasks with varying structural complexities and vocabularies?
- **RQ4 (Ablation Study):** How does each core component of HEX contribute to its overall performance?

Table 1. Summary of healthcare tasks used for evaluation

Task	Task Description	Task Query	Categories	Size
Hospitals	Hospitals located across various cities and municipalities.	Find me all the hospitals located in Ontario.	General Hospitals, Acute care Hospitals, Teaching Hospitals, Specialized Hospitals	158
Community Mental Health	Community-based centres that provide mental health services on an outpatient basis	Community mental health services in Ontario	Counselling, Therapy, Treatment, Medication	193
Addiction treatment	Withdrawal and treatment programs for individuals experiencing addiction in Ontario.	Retrieve addiction treatment programs in the Ontario.	Alcoholism, Drug addiction, Compulsive gambling, Eating disorders, Food Addiction, Opioid and Methadone Treatment, Behavioral Cognitive Therapy	227

Tasks: We select the healthcare domain for evaluation of HEX due to its high linguistic complexity and the dynamic nature of real-world healthcare data. While existing QA benchmarks [21] [18] exist where an agent terminates execution after a few steps to retrieve a single precise answer, the comprehensive retrieval tasks remain largely under-explored. In this setting, the goal shifts from retrieving a precise answer to discovering, verifying, and aggregating all relevant entities and their attributes, often numbering in the hundreds. To design our tasks, we use Ontario 211⁵ as our primary data source because it provides a reliable, human-vetted referral index. Ontario 211 provides entities (healthcare services names) alongside their attributes (location, contact and service descriptions). To ensure freshness and clear geographic boundaries, we limit our dataset to resources located within Ontario that were updated within the last five years. We strictly followed the Ontario 211 researcher guidelines to scrape data and manually verified it to ensure accuracy.

Building standardized datasets for CIR is challenging due to the massive scale and open-ended complexity of the underlying tasks. This required us to systematically design tasks that scale in difficulty. We created three distinct tasks to evaluate agent performance across a spectrum of navigational and vocabulary complexities, ranging from straightforward to highly difficult. The *Hospital* task is straightforward because hospital names are highly standardized and their websites follow structured layouts. In contrast, the *Community Mental Health* and *Addiction Treatment* tasks introduce much higher difficulty. These domains feature overlapping organizational boundaries and highly diverse, specific terminologies that thoroughly test an agent’s semantic understanding and web exploration policies. The complete structural properties, queries, and entity counts of these three tasks are summarized in Table 1.

Evaluation To evaluate our framework, we utilized Precision and Recall. We employed a hybrid evaluation pipeline consisting of an exact-match followed by a human verification. First, we performed an exact-match on the healthcare entity names against the Ontario 211 dataset. This initial step effectively narrowed down the pool of hundreds of retrieved entities to those present in the reference dataset.

⁵ <https://211ontario.ca/>

Second, we conducted human evaluation on the corresponding entity attributes, specifically assessing addresses and contact details. An entity was marked as a true positive (relevant) only if its address, contact details, and service name were entirely accurate. For descriptive attributes, such as the service description, human evaluator checked for semantic alignment with the Ontario 211 reference text, verifying that the text described healthcare services specific to the input query.

Baselines:

- **HTML-RAG [16]:** This model follows a direct retrieval-to-inference approach. It utilizes a search engine to retrieve relevant web pages and downloads the HTML of webpages. Then, it feeds the raw HTML directly into the LLM to generate an answer.
- **ReAct [20]:** This framework provides a Thought, Action, and Observation loop to build an AI agent. In this model, the agent describes its reasoning to complete a task, selects a specific tool, and then an agent executor runs the tool and feeds the result back to the model as an observation. This baseline is implemented using LangGraph, which provides extensive support for orchestrating ReAct agents.
- **Rewrite-Retrieve-Read (R^3) [10]:** This model utilizes an LLM to rewrite the input query. The reformulated query is used to retrieve relevant webpages from search engine, webpages are subsequently read by the LLM to generate the final output. In our baseline, we follow their few-shot query rewriting strategy.
- **LLM-assisted Pseudo Relevance Feedback:** In this baseline, we extend R^3 framework by applying pseudo-relevance feedback (PRF). Given an input query, the model first performs an initial retrieval to obtain top-ranked webpages using R^3 pipeline. An LLM-based relevance judge is then used to assess the relevance of each retrieved web page with respect to the query, assigning a relevance score between 0 and 1. Webpages with scores above 0.5 are treated as pseudo-relevant. Salient terms are extracted from pseudo-relevant documents using TF-IDF weighting, are used to guide the query rewriter. The rewriter reformulates the input query, are issued to retriever for a second round of retrieval. Reader processes the retrieved webpages to generate the final output. This process enables feedback-driven query reformulation by leveraging contextual signals from the initial retrieval.

6 Results and Discussion

6.1 Main Results (RQ1):

Evaluating macro-regional healthcare entity table generation is challenging task because existing benchmarks primarily target document retrieval, or question answering rather than the comprehensive construction of entity tables across

Table 2. Comprehensive Evaluation Across Baselines and Healthcare Tasks

Task	Model	Recall	P@10	P@100
Hospitals	HTML RAG	0.191	1.000	–
	ReAct	0.460	1.000	–
	R^3	0.143	1.000	–
	LLM-based PRF	0.434	1.000	–
	HEX (Ours)	0.986	1.000	0.990
Community Mental Health	HTML RAG	0.036	0.700	–
	ReAct	0.046	0.800	–
	R^3	0.051	1.000	–
	LLM-based PRF	0.093	0.900	–
	HEX (Ours)	0.948	1.000	0.920
Addiction Treatment	HTML RAG	0.074	0.800	–
	ReAct	0.039	0.900	–
	R^3	0.061	1.000	–
	LLM-based PRF	0.088	1.000	–
	HEX (Ours)	0.886	1.000	0.970

Note: long-dash (–) entries indicate that the baseline terminated execution early and failed to retrieve sufficient entities to compute precision@100.

different regions. Therefore, we compare HEX against standard RAG and QA baselines to establish a reference benchmark. This evaluation assesses whether precision-oriented retrieval architectures can achieve high recall on macro-regional queries. The results indicate that completeness is primarily determined by architectural design rather than prompting strategies alone. Table 2 shows the performance of all baselines and HEX across the three healthcare tasks. The baseline recall decreases as the search tasks becomes larger and more complex. For the Hospitals task, the best baseline achieves a recall of 0.460. However, recall drops below 0.10 on both Community Mental Health and Addiction Treatment, reaching as low as 0.036. This suggests that existing RAG and agent-based frameworks have difficulty finding a large number of relevant entities for macro-regional search tasks.

On the other hand, HEX achieves a higher recall across all tasks, with scores of 0.986, 0.948, and 0.886 for Hospitals, Community Mental Health, and Addiction Treatment, respectively. At the same time, HEX maintains precision ($P@10 = 1.000$) and deep precision, with $P@100$ values ranging from 0.920 to 0.990. These results show that the verification state of HEX remove irrelevant entities while keeping high coverage of relevant ones. The baseline methods stop before exploring enough of the search space. This is shown by the missing (–) values for $P@100$, which indicate that these methods did not retrieve enough entities for evaluation at a depth of 100. In contrast, HEX retrieves a large number of entities and maintains strong performance across all three tasks.

6.2 Analysis (RQ2):

The results in Table 2 demonstrate how HEX maximizes entity recall while maintaining high deep precision ($P@100$). Agentic frameworks, such as ReAct, rely on monolithic reasoning loops that are vulnerable to localized bottlenecks. It lacks an inherent mechanism for query reformulation, limiting the diversity of its results, and frequently experiences termination when encountering dense web directories or repetitive entity structures. On the other hand, RAG framework only retrieve top-k results, they lacked exploration strategies. HEX addresses these limitations through its spatial query decomposition. By decomposing the macro-region query into sub-regions and reformulating queries for each decomposition, the web search horizon is structurally enforced rather than remaining dependent on an agent’s internal stopping criteria. This allows the agent to continue discovering entities deep into the target search space. HEX also maintains precision ($P@100$ of 0.990 in Hospitals and 0.970 in Addiction Treatment) because its verification step filters out irrelevant entities, ensuring that expanded coverage does not introduce false positives.

Further analysis indicates that executing the pipeline costs between \$5 and \$7 USD with an execution latency of 25 to 30 minutes per task using GPT-4o. While these metrics are higher than standard precision-oriented RAG baselines, this overhead represents a necessary trade-off for stakeholders requiring comprehensive entity tables rather than simple top- k lookups. Although we attempt to mitigate excessive token consumption via HTML-to-Markdown conversion and DBpedia-guided query reformulation, scaling this framework to larger geographic regions presents clear cost and latency challenges. Future work can focus on exploring strategies to reduce both financial cost and operational latency.

6.3 Task Generalization (RQ3):

The performance of HEX across the healthcare tasks demonstrates its capacity to domain-specific structural complexities and vocabularies. As the search tasks transition from standardized domains like Hospitals to specialized domains like Addiction Treatment, the baseline models experience an exponential performance decay. For example, recall of ReAct drops from 0.460 to 0.039. HEX generalizes robustly against these variations, maintaining a high recall of 0.886 even on the most complex Addiction Treatment task because HEX utilizes systematic spatial decomposition which isolates the retrieval process from the vocabulary complexity of the target domain. Instead of getting trapped by semantic keyword drifts, HEX enforces structured geographic coverage.

6.4 Ablation Study (RQ4):

To observe where gains of HEX comes from we conducted a detailed ablation study.

Closed-book GPT-4o: To evaluate whether closed-book LLM can achieve comprehensive regional coverage, we establish a baseline by querying a closed-book GPT-4o model over five independent runs, aggregating unique extractions while removing duplicates. The empirical results demonstrate a collapse in recall, yielding only 15/152 (9.9%) for Hospitals, 10/193 (5.2%) for Community Mental Health, and 10/227 (4.4%) for Addiction Treatment across all five combined runs.

Qualitative analysis reveals that multi-run aggregation fails to overcome structural biases inherent to LLM. In the addiction task, the model misses niche services across Northern Ontario and overlooks major clinical infrastructure in Southern Ontario hubs like Hamilton and Waterloo, restricting its outputs to prominent facilities in Toronto and its immediate suburban periphery (e.g., Whitby and Etobicoke).

Similarly, for community mental health, the model retrieves famous services in cities like Kitchener, Hamilton, Ottawa, and North Bay, like the Centre for Addiction and Mental Health (CAMH) while omitting localized, niche centers. The hospitals task likewise plateaus at 15 prominent facilities, completely missing vital regional hospitals in neighboring mid-sized cities such as Guelph and Windsor. Beyond these spatial limitations, the closed-book LLM is restricted by temporal decay and vocabulary constraints. For instance, it identifies a major Kitchener facility by its legacy name, *Grand River Hospital*, failing to capture its updated structural alignment under the *Waterloo Regional Healthcare Network*. These findings demonstrate that retrieval is central to this task.

Without Planning States In this ablation, we evaluate the impact of the planning stage, specifically isolating the roles of query decomposition and query reformulation within the HEX framework. Together, these two states generate sub-regional queries that drive high recall for the macro-regional queries. Without these two planning states, HEX reverts to a standard Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) framework, matching the baseline performance of HTML-RAG shown in Table 2. The removal of the decomposition and reformulation stages in HEX forces the search engine into a strict keyword-matching bottleneck, leaving it unable to aggregate healthcare entities from multiple different geographical regions.

Without Verification: To isolate the impact of the verification module, we evaluate a HEX variant that appends all retrieved entities directly to the final table without verification. While omitting this stage preserves recall as valid target entities remain within the retrieved pool, it introduces substantial noise that degrades precision. Without verification, Precision@100 drops to 0.82 for Hospitals, 0.67 for Community Mental Health, and 0.54 for Addiction Treatment. Qualitative analysis reveals two distinct noise categories: geographical and semantic. Geographical noise includes entities outside the target macro-region, such as facilities in Montreal or Waterloo, USA.

Semantic noise occurs because HEX fails to enforce domain boundaries without verification. For the Hospitals task, the baseline includes adjacent facilities

like independent emergency rooms alongside full hospitals. In the Community Mental Health task, the output contains private psychiatrists, counseling centers, and general healthcare services that do not meet the definition of community mental health. The Addiction Treatment task exhibits the highest semantic drift, incorporating irrelevant social services such as dental clinics, homeless shelters, and drop-in centers. These results demonstrate that while query planning drives recall, the verification module is required to enforce semantic intent and filter out-of-domain entities.

7 Conclusion & Future work

In this study, we define table generation tasks as a high-recall retrieval problem, termed as comprehensive retrieval. We introduced HEX, a six-state agentic framework that perform exhaustive entity discovery. Our evaluation across three complex healthcare domain tasks demonstrates that HEX increases entity recall while maintaining precision. Our findings reveal that geographical decomposition and query reformulation are driving factors for the HEX recall gains, while verification stage is important to enforce semantic and geographical boundaries for entities retrieved from the Web

While HEX achieves high recall and precision, it has some limitations that point to future research directions. Web table generation in healthcare is sensitive to real-time changes like clinic closures or displacement. HEX processes web data at a single point in time and cannot incrementally track updates; therefore, future research can explore strategies to track those changes. While this study evaluates HEX for healthcare tasks, future work can expand the evaluation to open-domain settings, such as legal and entertainment queries, to test its domain generalizability across varied schemas and vocabularies.

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